

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КАЧЕСТВ У БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ ФАКТОРЫ

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Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kun talabi tarbiyachining kasbiy mahorat, bilimdonligi, zukkoligi, ijodkorligi bilan birga shaxsiy sifatlarni ham takomillashtirishni ham taqozo qiladi. Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak tarbiyachining pedagogik mahorati va kasbiy madaniyatini oshirishdagi muammolari haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik qobiliyat, pedagogik texnika, pedagogik kvalimetriya, pedagogik munosabat.

Abstract. Today's demand is professional skills, knowledge, along with intelligence and creativity, it also requires improvement of personal qualities. This article talks about the problems of improving the pedagogical skills and professional culture of the future educator.

Key words: pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique, pedagogical qualimetry, pedagogical attitude.

Абстрактный. Сегодня востребованы профессиональные навыки, знания, наряду с интеллектом и творческим потенциалом требует также совершенствования личностных качеств. В данной статье говорится о проблемах повышения педагогического мастерства и профессиональной культуры будущего воспитателя.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая способность, педагогическая

техника, педагогическая квалиметрия, педагогическое отношение.

The scientific approaches of recent years have made it possible to draw the following conclusion in relation to this situation: pedagogical skill is understood as a bright manifestation of individuality in professional activity. In our opinion, compared to others, this definition more accurately illuminates the essence of pedagogical skills. "It is an art that provides the opportunity to reach a high level in education and training and to constantly improve it, it is the work of every pedagogue who loves the student and loves his profession. A pedagogue who is a master of his work is a highly cultured specialist, who knows his subject in depth, can analyze the relevant fields of science or art well, and has mastered the methodology of education and training perfectly. Humanity is the most important basis for the personality of a modern pedagogue. A teacher is a person with a very high level of culture. He needs to know a lot.

Nowadays, he should be aware of the achievements and news in the field of science he is studying. In order to teach students daily activities, he should regularly study, learn, fill and deepen his knowledge. Pedagogical skill is not an innate or hereditary trait, but a product of research and creative work. This multifaceted pedagogical activity is based on creative work. If we look at the professional skills program of the pedagogue in practice, then the first place is its integral quality - skill. Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspects of skill are definitely expressed in them.

Pedagogical culture of the educator is the personality of the educator is a generalizing feature, it reflects the ability to persistently and successfully implement educational activities in effective cooperation with children and children. Pedagogical practice without such a pedagogical culture is boring and

ineffective. It is precisely the study and analysis of the principle of anthropocentrism in the development of the pedagogical culture of future educators and its application to practice that creates the phenomenon of today's modern educator. The requirement for an educator is, first of all, to conduct research on himself. Therefore, the most important need in the preschool education system is the development of pedagogical maturity of preschool education organization specialists. Improving the methodology of developing pedagogical culture among future teachers working in pre-school educational organizations based on the principle of anthropocentrism shows the personal example of educators in demonstrating their positive qualities in any process and a responsible approach to the pedagogical situation.

First of all, preschool education requires pedagogical culture from pedagogues and educators through the development of individual abilities of the growing young generation that can fully respond to the requirements of the new age, can approach moral values. It is the responsibility of the pedagogues of the higher education institution to develop the pedagogical culture of the future educators and specialists of the preschool educational organization, whose role in raising a perfect person is incomparable, means honesty, correctness. Pedagogical tact (tact) in the system of pedagogical skills is the pedagogy of the pedagogue measure, measure and impact of appropriate, useful, valuable actions is characterized as the limit of the tool. The listed components of pedagogical skill enrich the professional characteristics of the pedagogue and lead him to mastery, and help the educator to develop pedagogical skills. However, relying solely on them to become a master of your profession may not yield the expected results. For this, it is necessary to regularly think pedagogically, think pedagogically, and do

pedagogic work. This means that it is necessary to analyze the pedagogical events and situations of one's activity, to try to understand their connections, to independently analyze the daily results and to get used to comparing new educational ideas with the previous ones. It is necessary to find the main pedagogical and psychological problems and to think about finding the most convenient ways to solve them.

Humanism is a concept that expresses concern for the creation of conditions for the manifestation of all the principles of humanity, about human dignity, freedom, happiness and equal rights. Taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of pedagogues, the correct use of their capabilities; correct attitude towards predictable situations, rational assessment of others' success, fairness in material and moral incentives. The scientific essence of the article. The process of developing pedagogical culture in future teachers requires a systematic and active approach. Of course, taking into account the main goals and tasks of the anthropocentrism approach to the educational process mentioned above, it is necessary to clarify each stage, criteria, forms, methods and tools of this process, and to use them effectively. Therefore, based on the purpose of the research, a model for the development of pedagogical culture of future teachers was developed. This model reflects the goal of developing the pedagogical culture of the future teachers of the higher education system and the expected result based on it. It also defines the stages of the process, the main pedagogical conditions, the forms, methods and means of organizing activities, as well as the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications that must be mastered by students. Development of pedagogical culture in future educators as one of the main factors of ensuring the effectiveness of the teacher, first of all, in developing the training

project, determining the main goal, and defining the pedagogical tasks, the professor takes into account the existing conditions, the level of knowledge of the students, and their interests, as well as the best way to achieve the set goal should be able to choose effective ways and methods and have the ability to use them in the teaching process.

REFERENCES:

1. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "For 2022-2026 "On the development strategy of new Uzbekistan" (National database of legislative information.
2. Darvishov Ibrahim Ormonovich phd, associate professor INGOCULTUROLOGY Text of Lectures on Science 70230100 - Linguistics (Uzbek language) specialization for master's degree NAMANGAN - 2021
3. Pedagogy: 1000 answers to 1000 questions/ Methodological guide. U.I. Inoyatov, N.A. Muslimov, M. Usmanboyeva, D. Inoghamova. - T.: TDPU named after Nizami, 2012.
4. Hoshimov K and others. History of pedagogy //Pedagogy higher educational institutions and Study guide for dorilfunul students. - Tashkent, Okhtuchy, 1996, - page 301.
5. Mahkamov U, Tillaboeva N, Tillaboeva SH. Pedagogical skills. Education manual. T.: 2003